

Metal Ion Interactions with the Constituents of Nucleic Acid. Part-I : Metal-Adenine Complexes

R. G. BHATTACHARYYA and (Mrs.) I. BHADURI

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 082

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Metal-adenine complexes of the type $[Cd(AdH)_2Cl_2]$, $[Hg_2Cl_2Ad_2(AdH)]$, $[Pd_2Cl_2Ad_2(AdH)]2H_2O$ and $[UO_2(Ad)_2(H_2O)_2]H_2O$ have been isolated and characterised by analytical, infrared and TGA data. The AdH (neutral adenine) is probably unidentate in the Cd complex whereas in the Hg and Pd complexes, it functions probably as a bidentate bridging ligand, linking two metal ions. In the case of the Pd complex, Ad coordinates through C(6) NH_2 and N(7) but in all other cases possibly through N(3) and N(9) atoms.

THE biologically important intermolecular transfer of a phosphoryl group of adenosine triphosphate is an enzymic process with an absolute metal ion requirement. The non-enzymic transphosphorylation occurring between ATP and orthophosphate is also catalysed by bivalent metal ions, notably Mn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and Cd^{2+} . In a recent publication² we described the synthesis and characterisation of some metal-ATP complexes with particular emphasis on the binding sites. Adenine, one of the constituent bases of nucleic acids and the constituent base of ATP, is known³ to enter into metal coordination either as a neutral molecule, AdH, or as a mono-anion, Ad [by the deprotonation of N(9) i.e. the imino nitrogen]. In acid medium the base also coordinates as adeninium cation, AdH_2^+ , where apart from N(9) [where one proton normally resides in free neutral adenine but if this nitrogen is linked with metal on coordination, the proton shifts to N(7)³], N(1) is also protonated^{4,5}.

The earlier work^{6,7} regarding the preparation of the Au(III) adenine complex in dil HCl medium probably involves adenine in the form of the cation AdH_2^+ . Only comparatively recently the Cu(II), Zn(II) and Pt(II) complexes with adenine have been isolated and their structures studied⁸⁻¹⁰. In this paper, we report the complexes of adenine with Cd(II), Hg(II), Pd(II) and $UO_2(II)$.

Experimental

Preparation of the complexes: The Cd(II), Hg(II) and Pd(II) complexes are prepared by adding an aqueous solution of adenine in twice molar proportion to the respective metal chloride solution in water (aqueous NaCl in the case of $PdCl_2$). The precipitated solids (the pH of the medium after the precipitation of the complexes remains at 5) were washed with hot water, ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum.

In the case of dioxouranium(VI) complex, the aqueous solution of $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and adenine

were mixed in 1 : 2 molar ratio but the resultant solution was clear. The pH was raised to 5 by adding NaOH solution and the precipitated solid was washed and dried as in the other cases.

The compounds are insoluble in water as well as in all organic solvents.

Materials and methods: All chemicals used were of analytical grade. The infrared spectra ($4000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) as CsI pellets were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer Model 597 IR spectrophotometer. The water content and the decomposition temperatures were followed from the TGA curves².

Results and Discussion

The composition of the complexes and their analytical data are recorded in Table 1. The composition of the complexes, suggested on the basis of their analytical data is further corroborated by their infrared vibrational frequencies. In molecules like adenine, the intensity of the νNH_2 bands ($\sim 3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is expected¹¹ to be not much greater than that of the νNH ($\sim 3150\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The position and relative intensities of the infrared bands may therefore be considered here as reasonable guide in deciding ligand type (neutral, anionic or cationic) and the probable binding sites. Making proper allowance for any intermolecular hydrogen bonding (specially in the free adenine molecule) and roughly analysing the overlapping NH_2 and NH bands as per Gaussian method, it appears that in adenine (3250, 3050) the intensity of the said bands are in the ratio 1 : 1 and so also in the Cd compound (3300, 3135), but in the Hg compound (3325, 3050) the intensity of the former band is roughly double of that of the latter. These observations support the suggested compositions. Strong water absorption of the uranium compound as well as the medium intensity broad water band in the palladium complex frustrate such an attempt.

Comparing the positions of the four δNH_2 bands¹² in free adenine [1675 (s), symmetric in

TABLE I—THE COMPOSITION, COLOUR, ANALYTICAL AND THE INFRARED DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compounds	Colour	Analysis%				(M-Cl) [*] cm ⁻¹	(M-N) [†] cm ⁻¹
		M Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	Cl Found (Calcd.)	H ₂ O Found (Calcd.)		
CdCl ₂ (AdH) ₂	White	25.1 (24.8)	31.4 (30.9)	16.2 (15.7)	—	340	542
Hg ₂ Cl ₂ (AdH)(Ad) ₂	White	45.1 (45.8)	24.0 (24.0)	9.2 (8.1)	—	338	545
Pd ₂ Cl ₂ (AdH)(Ad) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Yellow	29.4 (29.7)	28.3 (29.0)	10.4 (9.8)	4.7 (5.0)	325	445
UO ₂ (Ad) ₂ ·3H ₂ O	Yellow	39.6 (40.1)	23.9 (23.6)	—	9.4 (9.1)	—	400

* Ref. 14c-16 ; † Ref. 14a-18.

plane ; 1250 (m), asymmetric out of plane ; 910 (m), symmetric out of plane and 718 (m), asymmetric in plane deformation] and metal bound adenine (bands almost retain their positions), it is clear that

Fig. 1. The infrared spectra of (1) Cd complex, (2) Hg complex, (3) Pd complex and (4) UO₂ complex.

unlike the ATP complexes² [the bands described¹ as $\nu(\text{CN})$ should be the symmetric in plane deformation of the NH_2 group in ATP and its complexes ; other δNH_2 bands are also there] the bands here do not undergo red shift (rather slightly blue shifted) on complexation, excepting in the case of Pd(II) complex, where it does [1645 (s), 1218 (m) ; 910 cm^{-1} band not observed]. This observation excludes the possibility of coordination through the C(6) NH_2 group in all the cases except that of the Pd(II), where the coordination definitely occurs through the said NH_2 group (see Fig. 1 for comparison). Modelling¹³ indicates that involvement of the NH_2 group in coordination almost commits the participation of the N(7) of adenine. It may, therefore, be concluded that in the Pd(II) complex, Ad functions as a bidentate ligand linking through C(6) NH_2 and the N(7). Since in the said complex only a single type of NH_2 group is found from the ir data, the AdH probably functions as a bridging ligand between two Pd(II) groups—one linked to N(7) and the other to C(6) NH_2 group (Fig. 2A). This contention is also supported by the $\nu(\text{Pd}-\text{Cl})$ vibration (325 cm^{-1}) which indicates that chloride is present as a terminal ligand and not a bridging one^{14c}. Similarly, in the Cd and Hg complexes the $\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})$ band (Table 1) is indicative of terminal chloride ligands. No other band at still lower wave number regions is present in any of the cases (Fig. 1) thereby ruling out the possibility of a bridging M-Cl bond (see also refs. 15 and 16). It may also be quite pertinent to mention here that $[\text{Cu}_2\text{Ad}_2]$ (prepared by the method of Weiss and Venner⁸ and ir spectra recorded by us for comparison) complex is ir transparent in the region 400-200 cm^{-1} . However, in the Pd complex, as expected, the ring vibrations¹¹ of the purine ring is only very slightly modified after the involvement of the N(7) during metallation. In fact, the ring vibrations in the other cases (Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} and UO_2^{2+}) are a bit more modified. Based on these observations, and also the fact that in the latter two cases the NH_2 group remains free, it may be presumed that Ad⁻ in these cases functions as a bidentate ligand linking through N(3) and N(9) (Figs. 2B and 2C) as was confirmed in the case of Cu(II) by X-ray crystallography⁸. In the Hg(II)

complex, AdH probably acts as a bridging group linking through two Hg(II) ions, one with N(3) and the other with N(9), since here also only one type of NH₂ mode is present and the possibility of chlorine bridging is excluded from the far ir spectroscopy. Since the Cd(II) complex should be 4-coordinated, the AdH groups probably act here as a unidentate ligand linking through the N(9) (Fig. 2D), a site which might be preferred to N(3) (compare the nucleoside formation by linking through sugars at this point).

After a thorough comparison of the ir bands of adenine with those of the complexes, the $\nu(U-N)$ is assigned¹⁷ at 400 while the $\nu(Pd-N)$ band at

Fig. 2. The most probable structures of (A) Pd complex, (B) Hg complex, (C) UO₂ complex and (D) Cd complex.

445^{14a} and the $\nu(Cd/Hg-N)$ bands in the vicinity of 540 cm⁻¹ (Table 1). The Cd and Hg-N vibrations at higher wave numbers are also corroborated by earlier work on the N-chelates^{14a}. The UO₂²⁺ complex contains two other bands, one at 320 and the other at 260 cm⁻¹. The latter band is assigned to the ν_2 (bending vibration)^{19,20} of the UO₂²⁺ ion while the former is assignable to the $\nu(U-O)$ band arising out of the water ligands^{14b,20-22}.

TGA curves show that the water molecules in the Pd(II) complex and one of the water molecules in the UO₂²⁺ complex are lost well below 100° indicating that they are only weakly held in the lattice. Other water molecules present in the appropriate cases are lost just below 150° showing that they are coordinated. (However the δH_2O bands are entrapped within the strong δNH_2 absorption). All these confirm the suggested structures (Fig. 2).

The compounds are insoluble and the possibility of molecular polymerisation could not be ruled out. Also, the insolubility of the complexes even in DMSO did not permit any NMR work which would have been more conclusive. They are prepared under such a condition that isolation of good crystals are impossible. So, presently, our knowledge should remain limited to the formulation of the most probable structures (Fig. 2A-2D).

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Preparation and Characterization of Naphthoxides of Niobium(V) and Tantalum(V)

K. C. MALHOTRA, (Miss) GEBTA MATHUR, K. C. MAHAJAN and S. C. CHAUDHRY

Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh University, Simla-171 005

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Compounds of composition $MCl_n(ONp)_{3-n}$, where $M=Nb$ or Ta , ONp =anion of β -naphthol and $n=0$ to 4, have been prepared by digesting pentachlorides of the metals with β -naphthol in appropriate molar ratios in carbon tetrachloride. Their structures have been elucidated from elemental analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared and TGA studies.

COMPARED to alkoxides, very little work has been carried out on the synthesis of metal phenoxides and naphthoxides, inspite of their utility as catalysts in many industries¹. Prasad and coworkers² isolated two series of compounds of anhydrous aluminium chloride with β -naphthol. Halides of titanium(IV) and zirconium(IV) are known to react with phenols and naphthols to form the corresponding derivatives but their structural information is lacking³. Reaction of selenium dithiocyanate with naphthols has been found to be useful for introducing SCN group into organic compounds⁴. Naphthols have been reported to be most effective and convenient amongst the phenols for the separation of ruthenium from uranium⁵. Naphthoxides of beryllium(II) and tungsten(V) have been isolated by reacting their halides with β -naphthol⁶. It is, therefore, of interest to isolate and characterise naphthoxides of transition metals. In the present communication, we report the preparation of naphthoxides of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) and propose a possible structure on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, TGA, magnetic and infrared spectral studies.

Experimental

Naphthol (A.R.) was purified by crystallisation from dry benzene. Pentachlorides of niobium and tantalum, were Fluka, analytical grade, and were used without further purification. All the organic solvents were of AnalaR grade. They were further dried by appropriate drying agents and fractionally distilled.

Compounds of composition $MCl_4(ONp)$, $MCl_3(ONp)_2$ and $MCl_2(ONp)_3$, where M stands for niobium or tantalum and ONp stands for the anion of β -naphthol, were obtained by mixing corresponding pentachlorides with β -naphthol in exact 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 molar ratio in dry carbon tetrachloride and continuous stirring at room temperature till there was no evolution of HCl gas. But in case of compounds of composition $MCl(ONp)_4$ and $M(ONp)_5$, the corresponding

mixture solutions were heated occasionally (not more than 60°). To ensure complete substitution by naphthoxy groups in the last compound, β -naphthol in 1 : 5 molar ratio was taken in a little excess and digested till there was no evolution of HCl gas. The compounds so obtained were filtered, washed repeatedly with dry benzene and finally dried under vacuum.

Niobium and tantalum were estimated as their pentoxides and chlorine by Volhard's method. Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded on a double grating infrared spectrophotometer, Perkin-Elmer 337 and 621, in KBr pellets. Molar conductance values of $10^{-8}M$ solutions of these compounds in nitrobenzene were determined using a cell of cell constant 0.384 at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge, CLOI/01A Sr. No. 447. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a Stanton thermogravimetric balance, model AD-2 at a heating rate of 5°/min. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Guoy's balance at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

The reactions of pentachlorides of niobium and tantalum with β -naphthol in carbon tetrachloride were found to be slow but became facile on digestion. All attempts to isolate a solvate of β -naphthol with pentachlorides of niobium and tantalum at room temperature were unsuccessful, possibly because of the greater lability of the proton of naphthol. The niobium compounds gave dull orange crystals whereas the tantalum compounds were sulphur yellow in colour. Stoichiometric composition of these compounds was established by elemental analysis and results are reported in Table 1. All these compounds are moisture sensitive and change their colour on exposure but are sufficiently stable in dry air. They are insoluble in most organic solvents except slight solubility in nitrobenzene and dimethylformamide. Molar conductance values of $10^{-8}M$ solutions in nitrobenzene (Table 1) suggest that the compounds are non-ionic